

STEPHOPOMA MAMILLATUM FROM THE CAPE VERDE ISLANDS

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In sediment samples from the Cape Verde Islands (São Nicolau and Sal) protoconchs of a peculiar vermetid were found. After examination we could identify it as *Stephopoma mamillatum* Morton & Keen, 1960, a species only known from its type locality «off Gorée, Sénégal». Figures of fullgrown specimens are given by MORTON & KEEN (1960). The colour of the protoconch is chestnut brown and it is sculptured with opisthocline rows of white vitreous, wartlike mammillae. Only the apex is smooth.

The genus *Stephopoma* has five species in the (Indo-) Pacific region, one dubious record from the Kattegat, North Sea (*Vermetus (Stephopoma) lyngbyanus* Mörch, 1871) and one species from East Panama (Caribbean) described by OLSSON & MCGINTY (1958) as *Stephopoma myrakeenae*.

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RESUMO

O autor refere uma extensão da distribuição geográfica de *Stephopoma mamillatum* Morton & Keen.

LITERATURE

- OLSSON, A. A. & T. L. MCGINTY, (1958) — Recent marine mollusks from the Caribbean coast of Panama, with description of some new genera and species. — *Bull. Amer. Paleont.* 39: 1-58.
- MORTON, J. E. & A. M. KEEN, (1960) — A new species of *Stephopoma* (Siliquariidae: Mesogastropoda) from the Eastern Atlantic Ocean. — *Proc. Mal. Soc. Lond.*, 34: 27-35.